

Synthesis of 1,3,5-thiadiazines from formamidinothiocarbamide

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Abstract : Novel series of 2-substitutedamino-4-(2-imino-4-thiobiureto-5-yl-carbamidino)-6-substitutedimino-1,3,5-thiadiazines (3a-f) and 2-substitutedamino-4-(4-imino-6-substitutedimino-1,3,5-thiadiaz-2-yl)-6-substitutedimino-1,3,5-thiadiazines (5a-f) has been obtained by basification of their hydrochlorides (2a-f) and (4a-f) respectively. The latter were synthesized by the interaction of 1-formamidino-3-thioamido-*N*-substitutedformamidinothiocarbamides (1a-f) and *N*-substitutedisocyanodichloride in 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 molar ratio respectively which were prepared initially by the condensation of aryl/alkylisothiocyanate and 1,3-diformamidinothiocarbamide in 1 : 1 molar ratio. The structure of all these compounds were established on the basis of elemental analysis, IR and PMR spectral data.

Keywords : 1,3,5-Thiadiazines, synthesis, substitutedthiocarbamides.

The literature survey reveals that the heterocyclic compounds having 1,3,5-thiadiazines nucleus enhanced pharmaceutical, medicinal, agricultural and industrial values¹. The synthetic applications of *N*-substitutedisocyanodichlorides have been investigated and shown to have enough potential in the synthesis of nitrogen and sulphur containing heterocyclic compounds² thus aim to synthesized 1,3,5-thiadiazines, reaction of *N*-aryl/alkylisocyanodichloride have been carried out with different 1-formamidino-3-thioamido-*N*-substitutedformamidinothiocarbamides in 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 molar ratios.

Experimental

All chemicals used were of analar grade. *N*-Substitutedisocyanodichlorides were prepared according to literature method³. Melting point of all synthesized compounds was determined in open capillary and uncorrected; IR spectra were recorded on Perkin-Elmer spectrometer in the range 4000–400 cm⁻¹ in Nujol mull as KBr pellets. PMR spectra were recorded with TMS as internal standard using CDCl₃ and DMSO-*d*₆. TLC checked the purity of the compounds on silica gel-G plates with layer thickness of 0.3 mm. All compounds gave satisfactory C, H, N and S elemental analysis.

The parent compound 1-formamidino-3-thioamido-*N*-substitutedformamidinothiocarbamide (1a-f) was prepared by refluxing the mixture of 1,3-diformamidinothiocarbamide with aryl/alkylisothiocyanate in 1 : 1 molar

ratio in acetone ethanol medium for 4 h on water bath.

Synthesis of 1-formamidino-3-thioamido-*N*-phenylformamidinothiocarbamide (1a) : Mixture of 1,3-diformamidinothiocarbamide (0.01 m), phenylisothiocyanate (0.01 m) in carbon tetrachloride (30 ml) was refluxed on water bath for 4 h in 1 : 1 molar ratio. The mixture was filtered and filtrate during distillation yielded the crystals of 1a. Yield 80%; m.p. 264 °C; IR spectra of compound shows $\nu(\text{N-H})$ 3356.6, $\nu(\text{C-H})(\text{Ar})$ 3131.3, $\nu(\text{C=N})$ 1635.4, $\nu(\text{C-N})$ 1294.7, $\nu(\text{C=S})$ grouping 1197.7, $\nu(\text{C-S})$ 777.9 and $\nu(\text{C=NH})$ grouping 1688.4 cm⁻¹. The PMR spectra of compounds showed signals due to N-H protons at δ 6.7776 ppm, Ar-H at δ 7.4657 ppm and the signal at δ 3.155 ppm is due to moisture in DMSO-*d*₆ and δ 1.25 ppm is due to DMSO. Elemental analysis (Found : C, 40.35; H, 4.10; N, 33.02; S, 21.48. Calcd. : C, 40.67; H, 4.40; N, 33.22; S, 21.69%).

Similarly, other compounds (1b-f) were synthesized and enlisted in Table 1.

Synthesis of 2-phenylamino-4-(2-imino-4-thiobiureto-5-yl-carbamidino)-6-phenylimino-1,3,5-thiadiazine (3a(ii)) :

1-Formamidino-3-thioamido-*N*-phenylformamidinothiocarbamide (0.01 m) (1a) was suspended in carbon tetrachloride medium (25 ml). To this a solution of *N*-phenylisocyanodichloride (0.01 m) was added in 1 : 1 molar proportions. The reaction mixture was refluxed on water bath for 4 h. During heating evaluation of hydro-

Table 1. Physical data of the synthesised compounds^a

Compd.	R	Yield (%)	M.p. (°C)	Molecular weight	Molecular formula
1a	Phenyl	80	264	295	C ₁₀ H ₁₃ N ₇ S ₂
1b	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	75	272	329	C ₁₀ H ₁₂ N ₇ S ₂ Cl
1c	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	82	254	310	C ₁₁ H ₁₆ N ₇ S ₂
1d	Ethyl	73	230	247	C ₆ H ₁₃ N ₇ S ₂
1e	Methyl	84	218	233	C ₅ H ₁₁ N ₇ S ₂
1f	<i>t</i> -Butyl	79	256	275	C ₈ H ₁₇ N ₇ S ₂

^aAll compounds gave satisfactory C, H, N and S analysis.

gen chloride gas was observed and tested with moist blue litmus paper. Cooling the reaction mixture and distilled off excess solvent crystals were separated out. And crystallized from aqueous ethanol. Yield 72%, m.p. 210 °C and identified as 2-phenylamino-4-(2-imino-4-thiobiureto-5-yl-carbamidino)-6-phenylimino-1,3,5-thiadiazine hydrochloride (**2a(i)**). On basification of (**2a(i)**) with ammonium hydroxide solution afforded free bases (**3a(i)**). It was recrystallised from aqueous ethanol, m.p. 195 °C.

Similarly, other compounds, (**2a(ii)** to **2f(iv)**) were synthesized from (**1a-f**) and which on basification yielded thiadiazines (**3a(ii)** to **3a(iv)**) and (**3b(ii)** to **3f(iv)**) by above mention method and enlisted in Table 2.

Properties of compound (**3a(i)**) :

It is light brown crystalline solid having m.p. 195 °C. From analytical data, molecular formula is C₁₇H₁₆N₈S₂, molecular weight 396. IR spectra of compound shows $\nu(\text{N-H})$ 3359.5, $\nu(\text{C-H})(\text{Ar})$ 2924.7, $\nu(\text{C=N})$ 1642.2, $\nu(\text{C-N})$ 1293.3, $\nu(\text{C=S})$ grouping 1173.7, $\nu(\text{C-S})$ 778.2 and $\nu(\text{C=NH})$ grouping 1506.1 cm⁻¹. The PMR spectra of compound showed signals due to Ar-H protons at δ 7.04–7.71 ppm, Ar-NH protons at δ 6.68–6.87 ppm, N-H protons at δ 4.2–4.3 ppm and the signal at δ 2.7–3.1 ppm is due to moisture in DMSO-*d*₆ and δ 0.75–2.2 ppm is due to DMSO. Elemental analysis (Found : C, 51.49; H, 3.99; N, 28.14; S, 16.12. Calcd. : C, 51.52; H, 4.04; N, 28.28; S, 16.16%). From these spectral, elemental and chemical data the compound (**3a(i)**) is 2-phenylamino-4-(2-imino-4-thiobiureto-5-yl-carbamidino)-6-phenylimino-1,3,5-thiadiazine.

Properties of compound (**3b(i)**) :

It is pale yellow crystalline solid having m.p. 190 °C. From analytical data, molecular formula is C₁₃H₁₆N₈S₂, molecular weight 348. IR spectra of compound shows $\nu(\text{N-H})$ 3355.1, $\nu(\text{C-H})(\text{Ar})$ 2922.4, $\nu(\text{C=N})$ 1687.7, $\nu(\text{C-N})$ 1294.5, $\nu(\text{C=S})$ grouping 1193.6, $\nu(\text{C-S})$ 776.9,

Table 2. Physical data of the synthesised compounds

Compd.	R	R ₁	Yield (%)	M.p. (°C)
3a(i)	Phenyl	Phenyl	68	195
3a(iv)	Phenyl	<i>t</i> -Butyl	65	182
3b(i)	Ethyl	Phenyl	62	190
3b(iii)	Ethyl	Ethyl	73	177
3c(i)	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	Phenyl	68	207
3c(ii)	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	79	219
3c(iii)	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	Ethyl	74	191
3d(i)	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	Phenyl	72	203
3d(ii)	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	76	227
3d(iii)	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	Ethyl	59	187
3d(iv)	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	<i>t</i> -Butyl	54	181
3e(i)	Methyl	Phenyl	62	184
3e(ii)	Methyl	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	69	189
3e(iii)	Methyl	Ethyl	76	172
3e(iv)	Methyl	<i>t</i> -Butyl	12	176
3f(ii)	<i>t</i> -Butyl	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	72	192
3f(iii)	<i>t</i> -Butyl	Ethyl	61	168
3f(iv)	<i>t</i> -Butyl	<i>t</i> -Butyl	59	176
5a(i)	Phenyl	Phenyl	62	265
5a(ii)	Phenyl	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	82	285
5a(iii)	Phenyl	Ethyl	89	245
5a(iv)	Phenyl	<i>t</i> -Butyl	77	254
5b(i)	Ethyl	Phenyl	75	245
5b(ii)	Ethyl	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	67	272
5b(iii)	Ethyl	Ethyl	69	226
5b(iv)	Ethyl	<i>t</i> -Butyl	73	235
5c(i)	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	Phenyl	59	279
5c(ii)	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	62	294
5c(iii)	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	Ethyl	69	252
5c(iv)	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	<i>t</i> -Butyl	74	254
5d(i)	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	Phenyl	72	269
5d(ii)	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	79	289
5d(iii)	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	Ethyl	81	212
5d(iv)	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	<i>t</i> -Butyl	68	223
5e(i)	Methyl	Phenyl	54	239
5e(ii)	Methyl	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	59	264
5e(iii)	Methyl	Ethyl	68	231
5e(iv)	Methyl	<i>t</i> -Butyl	71	242
5f(i)	<i>t</i> -Butyl	Phenyl	81	264
5f(ii)	<i>t</i> -Butyl	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	69	281
5f(iii)	<i>t</i> -Butyl	Ethyl	74	238
5f(iv)	<i>t</i> -Butyl	<i>t</i> -Butyl	69	234

^aAll compounds gave satisfactory C, H, N and S analysis.

Scheme 1

$\nu(\text{C}=\text{NH})$ grouping 1440.2 and $\nu(\text{C}-\text{H})$ 2852.4 cm^{-1} . The PMR spectra of compounds showed signals due to Ar-H protons at δ 7.4–7.5 ppm, thiadiazino protons at δ 6.84–7.1 ppm, $-\text{CH}_2$ protons at δ 2.95 ppm, $-\text{CH}_3$ protons at δ 1.24–1.63 ppm and the signal at δ 2.11–2.15 and 2.55–2.56 ppm is due to moisture in DMSO. Elemental analysis (Found : C, 44.35; H, 4.42; N, 33.05; S, 18.22. Calcd. : C, 44.83; H, 4.6; N, 32.18; S, 18.39%). From these spectral, elemental and chemical data the compound (3b(i)) is 2-ethylamino-4-(2-imino-4-thiobiureto-5-yl-carbamidino)-6-phenylimino-1,3,5-thiadiazines.

where, R = phenyl, *p*-chlorophenyl, *p*-tolyl, ethyl, methyl, *t*-butyl
 R₁ = phenyl, *p*-chlorophenyl, ethyl, *t*-butyl

Scheme 2

Synthesis of 2-phenylamino-4-(4-imino-6-phenylimino-1,3,5-thiadiaz-2-yl)-6-phenylimino-1,3,5-thiadiazine (5a(i)) :

1-Formamidino-3-thioamido-*N*-phenylformamidinothiocarbamide (0.01 m) (1a) was suspended in acetone ethanol medium (25 ml). To this a solution of *N*-phenylisocyanodichloride (0.02 m) was added. The reaction mixture was refluxed on water bath for 12 h. During heating evolution of hydrogen chloride gas was observed

and tested with moist blue litmus paper. After cooling the reaction mixture and distilled off excess solvent, solid crystals were separated out. And crystallized from aqueous ethanol. Yield 73%, m.p. 272 °C and identified as 2-phenylamino-4-(4-imino-6-phenylimino-1,3,5-thiadiaz-2-yl)-6-phenylimino-1,3,5-thiadiazine hydrochloride (4a(i)). On basification of (4a(i)) with ammonium hydroxide solution afforded free base (5a(i)). It was recrystallised from aqueous ethanol, m.p. 265 °C.

Similarly, other compounds, (4a(ii) to 4f(iv)) were synthesized from (1a-f). And which on basification yielded other thiadiazines (5a(ii) to 5a(iv)) and (5b(ii) to 5f(iv)) by above mention method and enlisted in Table 2.

Properties of compound (5a(i)) :

It is ivory crystalline solid having m.p. 265 °C. From analytical data; molecular formula is $\text{C}_{24}\text{H}_{19}\text{N}_9\text{S}_2$, molecular weight 497. IR spectra of compound shows $\nu(\text{N}-\text{H})$ 3308.4, $\nu(\text{C}-\text{H})(\text{Ar})$ 2360.7, $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$ 1660.5, $\nu(\text{C}-\text{N})$ 1332.7, $\nu(\text{C}=\text{S})$ grouping 1154.2, $\nu(\text{C}-\text{S})$ 750 and $\nu(\text{C}=\text{NH})$ grouping 1465.6 cm^{-1} . The PMR spectra of compound showed signals due to Ar-NH protons at δ 8.63 ppm, Ar-H protons at δ 7.14–7.85 ppm, NH_2 protons at δ 5.5 ppm, NH protons at δ 3.9 ppm and the signal at δ 2.58–2.59 ppm is due to moisture in DMSO- d_6 and δ 1.25 ppm is due to DMSO. Elemental analysis (Found : C, 57.73; H, 3.62; N, 25.15; S, 12.7. Calcd. : C, 57.95; H, 3.82; N, 25.36; S, 12.87%). From these spectral, elemental and chemical data the compound (5a(i)) is 2-phenylamino-4-(4-imino-6-phenylimino-1,3,5-thiadiaz-2-yl)-6-phenylimino-1,3,5-thiadiazine.

Properties of compound (5b(i)) :

It is bricks red crystalline solid having m.p. 245 °C. From analytical data; molecular formula is $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{19}\text{N}_9\text{S}_2$, molecular weight 348. IR spectra of compound shows $\nu(\text{N}-\text{H})$ 3383.9 and $\nu(\text{C}-\text{H})(\text{Ar})$ 3146.6, $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$ 1666.1, $\nu(\text{C}-\text{N})$ 1179.8, $\nu(\text{C}=\text{S})$ grouping 1007.6, $\nu(\text{C}-\text{S})$ 748.2, $\nu(\text{C}=\text{NH})$ grouping 1573.9 and $\nu(\text{C}-\text{H})$ 1391.8 cm^{-1} . The PMR spectra of compound showed signals due to Ar-H protons at δ 7.99–8.0 ppm, thiadiazino NH_2 protons at δ 6.9 ppm, $-\text{CH}_2$ protons at δ 3.25–3.27 ppm, $-\text{CH}_3$ protons at δ 2.55 ppm and the signal at δ 1.25 ppm is due to moisture in DMSO. Elemental analysis (Found : C, 53.32; H, 4.09; N, 28.01; S, 14.19. Calcd. : C, 53.42; H, 4.24; N, 28.06; S, 14.24%). From these spectral, elemental and chemical data the compound (5b(i)) is 2-ethylamino-4-(4-imino-6-phenylimino-1,3,5-thiadiaz-2-yl)-6-phenylimino-1,3,5-thiadiazine.

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